

**Variation of the Cataphoretic Speeds of Colloidal
Particles. Part VI. Further Experiments on
the Variation of the Cataphoretic Speeds
with Dilution of the Colloidal Solution
and in Presence of Added Electrolytes.**

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The results published in earlier parts (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 296; 1927, 4, 493; 1928, 5, 697; 1928, 5, 735; 1933, 10, 27) show on the one hand that the prevalent conception of the relation between the stability of a colloid and a critical coagulating potential, or, of the factors affecting the cataphoretic speed are unsatisfactory, and on the other hand that the variations in the cataphoretic speed with dilution of the sol, addition of electrolytes and non-electrolytes are of a very complicated nature. These measurements have helped us to some extent to understand the peculiarities of the factors affecting the cataphoretic speeds, such as the adsorption of ions, the distribution of the ions in the double layer and the state of aggregation. Thus Mukherjee, Roychoudhury and Biswas (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 381) have shown that various types of curves are obtained in the dilution of ferric hydroxide sol (*cf.* also S. N. Mukherjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 52, 63). With arsenious sulphide sol also, the speed-dilution curve depends on the specific nature of the sol. Working with ferric hydroxide sol and potassium chloride solutions, the above authors have found a considerable drop in the cataphoretic speed after coagulation of the sol with progress of time. Also it has been shown (Part V) that the order of decrease of the cataphoretic speed of arsenious sulphide sol by NaCl, KCl and LiCl is $\text{Li}^{\circ} > \text{Na}^{\circ} > \text{K}^{\circ}$, which is contrary to previous observations as also to the order of coagulating concentrations of these electrolytes.

In view of the multifarious types of results obtained which showed that the variation of the cataphoretic speed depended on the specific nature of the colloid, it was thought desirable to carry out our further experiments. The present paper deals with the cataphoretic speeds of (1) arsenious sulphide, silicic acid and aluminium hydroxide sols with the dilution of the sol; (2) aluminium hydroxide sol mixed with potassium chloride and potassium sulphate solutions; (3) ferric hydroxide sol mixed with potassium chloride, potassium sulphate, sodium chloride and lithium chloride solutions.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Sols.

(1) *Arsenious sulphide sol.*—The method of preparation of the sol was as described previously (Part II, *loc. cit.*, p. 497).

Ferric hydroxide sol.—The method of preparation was as described in Part IV, p. 736. The sol was dialysed against repeated changes of hot distilled water until the dialysate was nearly free from chloride (a period of about a month).

(3) *Silicic acid sol (samples A, B₁, B₂ and C).*—210 C.c. of Kahlbaum's concentrated hydrochloric acid (*pro analyse*) was diluted with 700 c.c. of conductivity water. In it, 525 c.c. of sodium silicate solution of 1.16 sp. gr. was added in a thin stream with continuous stirring. Then the sol was allowed to dialyse in a parchment bag against repeated changes of cold distilled water until a slight opalescence was obtained (a period of 6 days). The sol was kept stocked in the atmosphere of hydrogen (A).

Another sample was prepared in the same way as sol A but 1.7 times more dilute. A portion was taken out after dialysis for 10 days (B₁) and another portion after dialysis for one week more (B₂). Sample C was prepared in the same way as sample A, but dialysed in a current of running distilled water for 2 days. This sample was very unstable, setting rapidly to a gel in a few days.

(4) *Aluminium hydroxide sol (sample A).*—The aluminium hydroxide sol was prepared by adding slightly less than the equivalent amount of ammonium hydroxide solution (N/10) slowly and with vigorous stirring to a solution of aluminium chloride (N/10). The resulting sol was purified by dialysis in a parchment bag against repeated changes of distilled water, until a turbid sol was obtained.

Procedure.

Cataphoretic speeds at $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$ were measured by using two separate U-tubes having effective distance of 4.01 cm. and of 2.89 cm. respectively. The former was used for work with arsenious sulphide, ferric hydroxide (A), silicic acid and partly with aluminium hydroxide sols, while the latter tube was used for all other measurements. The difference in viscosity being small, the speed has not been corrected for its variations. Some of the measurements were carried out in duplicate to find the reproducibility of the results.

During the measurements considerable difficulties were experienced in many cases. The difficulties have been described in a separate paper. The present paper records only reliable and reproducible data.

Variation of Cataphoretic Speeds with Dilution of Sols.

Measurements with arsenious sulphide sol.—In conformity with previous measurements, an equiconducting solution of hydrochloric acid was used as upper liquid. The colour contrast for reading the position of the boundary and produced by a deep blue glass filter, in previous measurements with this sol, was found to be insufficient. A layer of dilute permanganate solution contained in a rectangular absorption vessel and interposed in the path of the light was found quite satisfactory. The sol appeared purple while the colourless upper liquid appeared violet. With the diluted sols another difficulty was met with. The potential gradient was repeatedly observed to be very high when the circuit of the potentiometer was first closed and gradually dwindled down to a minimum limiting value in an hour or more. With the sol diluted 1 to 20 a constant potential gradient was not even approximately attained. Moreover, at this dilution the upward speed was very small in comparison with the downward one. The more diluted sols showed a tendency to settle. The results are given in Table I and Fig. 1, curve 1.

TABLE I. (Fig. 1, curve 1).

Sp. conductivity of the undiluted arsenious sulphide sol
 $= 2.05 \times 10^{-6}$.

p_H of the supernatant liquid of the undiluted sol after coagulating it with $KCl=6.16$.

Dilution with equal vol. of water.	Direct Pot. gradient		Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	Reverse Pot. gradient		Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	Mean rate of migration $\times 10^5$.
	Before.	After.		Before.	After.		
Undiluted sol	0.542	0.552	59.6	0.534	0.520	61.9	60.7
	0.580	0.558	58.5	9.540	0.546	62.5	
1 : 1	0.599	0.691	68.3	0.616	0.610	61.0	65.5
	0.556	0.558	68.8	0.570	0.578	66.0	
1 : 5	0.634	0.619	55.3	5.624	0.624	53.8	53.1
	0.696	0.625	52.0	0.637	0.640	59.4	
1 : 10	0.652	0.652	67.8	0.704	0.689	63.3	67.0
	0.600	0.600	68.4	0.653	0.652	69.0	

Measurements on the effect of the dilution on the cataphoretic speed of arsenious sulphide sol (Mukherjee, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923; **A 103**, 102 ; also Parts II and III) are given in Fig. 1, curves 2, 3 and 4.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

One finds that the variation of the cataphoretic speed with dilution depends on the sample of sol worked with. Curve 2 shows that the speed is not materially affected by the dilution. Curves 3 and 4 show a continuous decrease at all dilutions and curve 1 is rather peculiar having a S-shape. These peculiarities in behaviour cannot be reconciled with the theoretical point of view which regards colloidal arsenious sulphide to behave as an electrolyte, *viz.*, a weak acid. There is no parallelism between the variation of the mobility of an

anion of an acid with the dilution of the acid and that of the cataphoretic speed of the colloidal particles of the arsenious sulphide sols. According to this point of view the mobility should continuously increase with the dilution. Apparently the valencies and the numbers per-unit surface of the primarily adsorbed ions, which together determine the surface density of the electric charge and the distribution of the ions in the double layer determine the cataphoretic speed. The adsorption of ions as opposed to surface dissociation offers the only rational theoretical basis for an elucidation of these variations.

Measurements with silicic acid sols.—This sol as prepared here tends to set as a gel (occasionally in the dialyser itself) and in most cases can hardly be stocked for more than one or two weeks. A solution of hydrochloric acid of equal p_H as the sol and made equiconducting with the sol by the addition of a few drops of a concentrated solution of Na_2SiO_3 , has been used as the upper liquid. Equiconducting HCl solution has also been tried with no better advantage than the above mixture. It is also desirable to use a mixture of HCl and Na_2SiO_3 which is both equiconducting and has the same p_H as the sol. A peculiarity observed with this sol is that sometimes a certain length near about the boundary or the whole of the sol sets to a gel in the tube. The gel formation is hastened on passage of current through the sol. The boundary of the gel moves without any apparent separation of the gel near the boundary from its main body. The cataphoretic speed of this sol varies greatly from sol to sol and is smaller than that of the usual suspensoid sols.

TABLE II.
Silicic acid sols.

Sol.	Upper liquid.	p_H	Upward movement.				Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	Pot. gradient	Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	Mean of rate of migration $\times 10^5$.
			Pot. gradient		Pot. gradient					
			Before.	After.	Before.	After.				
A*	HCl of equal p_H & Na_2SiO_3	1.9	0.714	0.612	12.6	0.496	0.557	17.94	15.27	
B ₁ *	HCl	2.5	0.553	0.508	Very small	0.553	..	Very small	Very small	
B _{1/2} **	HCl & NaCl	2.89	1.03	1.13	9.1	1.13	1.03	2.1	2.6	
B ₂ **	"	3.17	1.61	1.59	13.47	1.48	1.41	17.36	15.41	
C**	"	3.4	1.45	1.43	7.7	1.46	1.4	4.5***	6.1	

* Effective distance of the U-tube used was 4.01 cm.

** Effective distance of the U-tube used was 2.89 cm.

*** The sol sets to a jelly.

It has been reported in a paper recently communicated to this Journal that a mixture of HCl of the same p_H as the sol and Na_2SiO_3 serves as a suitable upper liquid for silicic acid sol. But Table III shows that for sol A, a mixture of HCl and Na_2SiO_3 does not give a constant potential gradient and moreover, a considerable rate of settling of the sol is observed. In the later part of our work we found that a mixture of NaCl and HCl as upper liquid gives a more satisfactory potential gradient. Sol A had already become very thick and showed signs of gel formation and it was not possible to take measurements using the above mixture as upper liquid. It is, however, interesting that both the upward and downward cataphoretic speeds increase on dilution of the sol. The measurements of cataphoretic speeds in Table III, therefore, although not satisfactory, enable us however to draw qualitative conclusions.

TABLE III. (Fig. 2, curve 5).

Silicic acid sol (A)

Dilution with equal vol of water.	Sp. conducti- vity.	p_H .	Pot. gradient		Rate of migra- tion $\times 10^5$.	Pot. gradient		Rate of migra- tion $\times 10^5$.	Mean of rate of migra- tion $\times 10^5$.
			Before.	After.		Before.	After.		
Conc. sol	0.005709	1.9	0.714	0.612	12.61	...	...	...	...
			0.612	0.547	5.75	0.496	0.557	17.94	15.27
			0.547	0.482	4.23	0.657	0.535	19.34	...
1:1	0.00288	2.3	0.687	0.619	16.24	0.605	0.568	20.84	18.54
			0.694	0.605	17.11	0.612	0.576	18.69	12.90
1:5	0.001047	2.4	0.678	0.648	21.79	0.693	0.553	78.65	50.22
			0.670	0.663	21.72	0.670	0.574	77.67	49.49
1:16	0.000884	3.0	0.559	0.588	22.1	0.588	0.529	96.99	59.54
			0.647	0.681	22.59	0.691	0.559	90.69	56.64
1:1*			0.703	0.703	3.95	...	...	...	...
			0.702	0.674	4.08	0.646	0.571	10.06	7.05

The potential gradient varies as much as 15%. This indicates ionic migrations and possibly interactions at the boundary which change the concentration of the electric carriers and the specific conductivities. The cataphoretic speeds gradually increase with the dilution.

* A HCl solution of the same p_H as the silicic acid sol was made equiconducting as the sol by the addition of NaCl solution. The sol, however, had become very thick and showed signs of gel formation.

The H^+ ion and Cl^- ion concentrations of these sols were measured by Mr. B. R. Majumdar and decrease with the dilution. As however the ideal conditions in the measurement of cataphoretic speeds could not be attained, it is not profitable at this stage to try to correlate the variation of the cataphoretic speed with the observed variations of absorbed H^+ and Cl^- ions on the surface of colloidal particles of silicic acid sol.

Aluminium Hydroxide Sol (Sample A) mixed with Electrolytes.

A slow rate of filling the tube is necessary in order to secure a sharp boundary. The opalescence of these sols is very weak and in order to ensure that the boundary can be seen to rise at the desirable rate the cathetometer was focussed on the upper meniscus of the upper liquid and the stop-cock was gradually opened until a slow motion of the meniscus was perceived in the cathetometer. With practice a sharp boundary can be obtained.

Attempts to measure the cataphoretic speeds of $Al(OH)_3$ sols (K and L) were unsuccessful. These sols had low specific conductivities (about 3×10^{-5}) and the p_H values were about 7.0. With one sample (L) it was possible to produce a definite boundary but as soon as the current was switched on, the sol rose upwards in streaks. Sometimes a more or less ill-defined boundary was formed which broke up again during the migration.

TABLE IV (Fig. 3, curves 6 & 7).

Aluminium hydroxide sol (A).

Dilution with equal vol of water.	Sp. Conductivity.	p_H .	Pot. gradient		Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	Pot. gradient		Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	Mean rate of migration $\times 10^5$.
			Before.	After.		Before.	After.		
Conc.	0.0009249		0.531	0.531	49.25	0.561	0.561	48.5	47.8
			0.592	0.57	44.5	0.607	0.607	60.8	—
1 : 1	0.0003327	4.05	0.561	0.558	50.87	0.575	0.600	51.6	50.98
1 : 5	0.000293		0.627	0.630	41.32	0.620	0.627	62.95	52.1
1 : 10	0.0001175		0.617	0.612	52.67	0.627	0.634	52.9	52.78

* At this dilution the boundary showed an initial erratic movement for a comparatively long time. In order to avoid this error, all the readings have been taken after the current has been allowed to flow for 10 minutes and then without switching off the current.

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

FIG. 5.

Fig. 3, curves 6 and 7 represent respectively the specific conductivities and the cataphoretic speeds against the dilution and curve 8 in the same figure represents the variation of the cataphoretic speed of another aluminium hydroxide sol (cf. Mukherjee, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 698).

With sol A, the specific conductivities decrease while the cataphoretic speed increases with the dilution. For curve 8 there is an initial increase (at dilution 1:1) and then tends to decrease somewhat.

The cataphoretic speeds of aluminium hydroxide sols with increasing concentrations of potassium chloride and sulphate are given in Tables V and VI.

TABLE V (Fig. 4, curve 9).

 Al(OH)₃ sol (A) and KCl.

Conc. of electrolyte in normality	Upward movement.		Rate of migration × 10 ⁵ .	Downward movement.		Mean rate of migration × 10 ⁵ .
	Pot. gradient Before.	Pot. gradient After.		Pot. gradient Before.	Pot. gradient After.	
0	1.311	1.311	52.07	1.39	1.37	53.09
..*	0.561	0.559	50.87	0.675	0.600	61.06
0.001*	0.590	0.594	55.35	0.576	0.620	55.60**
0.01*	0.635	0.618	41.93	0.642	0.627	42.98**
0.05	1.356	1.387	41.18	1.407	1.356	—**
0.10	1.311	1.333	40.3	1.33	1.307	49.32***

*A different cataphoretic tube was used for the measurements.

**Within a few minutes of the downward movement, the boundary separated into two layers, a thin above a thick one. On reversing the movement, the two boundaries coalesced and this phenomenon could be again repeated a number of times. The readings were always taken on the upper layer.

***Flocculated during the latter part of the movement, so the value is possibly affected by the gravitational fall of the bigger particles,

TABLE VI (Fig. 4, curves 10 and 11).

 Al(OH)₃ sol (A) and K₂SO₄.

Conc. of electrolyte in normality.	Upward movement.		Rate of migration × 10 ⁵ .	Downward movement.		Mean rate of migration × 10 ⁵ .
	Pot. gradient Before.	Pot. gradient After.		Pot. gradient Before.	Pot. gradient After.	
0	Vide TABLE VI					51.77
0.0005	0.0617	0.692	36.03	0.617	0.588	44.26
0.001	1.344	27.49	27.49	1.413	1.419	41.68
	1.414	1.475	28.00	1.516	1.485	38.34
0.000125	1.354	1.375	29.5	1.435	1.445	28.93
	1.375	1.415	37.87			
0.00166	1.344	1.354	19.79	1.364	1.364	32.58*

*Flocculates. There is a noticeable difference between upward and downward cataphoretic speeds.

For 0.001*N*-potassium chloride the speed shows an increase but decreases at higher concentrations up to 0.1*N* (coagulating region, curve 9). With K_2SO_4 , however, there is a continuous decrease. Fig. 4, curve 11 represents curve 10 on a magnified scale. As is to be expected the decrease of the speed is much greater with K_2SO_4 than with KCl. The cataphoretic speeds at the coagulating region differ considerably for the two electrolytes and show that the assumption of a critical coagulation potential is not justifiable.

Ferric Hydroxide Sol mixed with Electrolytic Solutions.

This sol is very sensitive towards electrolytes. The tube after the usual cleaning with hot chromic acid solution can only be used after it has been kept filled with conductivity water for a few hours. The liquid used in calomel vessels for measuring the potential gradient at the boundary. As a result the movement of the boundary gradually slows down sometimes accompanied by slight haziness at the boundary. This can be avoided by proper care. The results are given in Tables VII, IX, and X, Fig. V.

TABLE VII (Fig. 5, curve 12).

$Fe(OH)_3$ sol and KCl.

Conc. of electrolyte in normality.	Upward movement.			Downward movement.			Mean rate of migration $\times 10^5$.
	Potential gradient		Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	Potential gradient		Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	
	Before.	After.		Before.	After.		
0.00	1.746	1.867	59.23	1.746	1.603	82.94	71.08
0.001*	1.391	1.452	32.84	1.451	1.411	45.74	39.29
0.002*	1.364	1.401	31.34	1.431	1.411	43.39	37.36
0.01†	1.36	1.401	10.86	1.401	1.421	—	10.86(?)

* A sudden drop in the potential gradient on the addition of the electrolyte is observed. This has been dealt with in a separate paper.

† Complete flocculation took place.

TABLE VIII (Fig. 5, curve 13).

 $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol and NaCl.

Conc of electrolyte in normality.	Upward movement.			Downward movement.			Mean rate of migration $\times 10^5$.
	Potential gradient		Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	Potential gradient		Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	
	Before.	After.		Before.	After.		
0	1.746	1.867	59.23	1.746	1.603	82.94	71.08
0.0011	1.409	1.409	35.48	1.413	1.368	55.16	42.68
	0.98	1.01	38.5	0.966	0.966	46.59	
0.0025	1.409	1.429	35.31	1.389	1.452	43.61	40.16
0.0056	1.425	1.429	24.52	1.378	1.338	38.06	31.29
0.00687	1.419	1.413	24.72	1.051	0.6534	—	24.72

TABLE IX (Fig. 5, curve 14).

 $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol and LiCl.

Conc. of electrolyte in normality.	Upward movement.			Downward movement.			Mean rate of migration $\times 10^5$.
	Potential gradient		Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	Potential gradient		Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	
	Before.	After.		Before.	After.		
0	1.746	1.867	59.23	1.746	1.603	82.94	71.09
0.001*	1.006	1.317	94.98	1.416	1.374	57.89	47.65
	1.386	1.416	38.88	1.372	1.336	61.55	—
0.002†	1.374	1.403	28.81	1.374	1.342	60.15	44.48
0.005‡	2.355	1.868	24.58	1.311	1.295	55.0	39.70

* A sudden drop in the potential gradient on the addition of electrolyte is observed. This has been dealt with in a separate paper.

† Complete flocculation took place.

‡ The sol became hazy and coagulated partially within a few minutes.

TABLE X (Fig. 5, curves 15 and 16).

 $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol and K_2SO_4 .

Conc. of electrolyte in normality.	Upward movement.		Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	Downward movement.		Rate of migration $\times 10^5$.	Mean rate of migration $\times 10^5$.
	Potential gradient			Potential gradient			
	Before.	After.		Before.	After.		
0	1.746	1.867	59.23	1.746	1.603	82.94	71.08
.000039*	1.989	1.419	21.87	1.419	1.41	40.05	30.71
.00005†	1.951	1.491	16.79	1.512	1.451	16.83	
	1.491	1.491	16.77	1.461	1.501	19.57	17.54
.000058†	1.855	1.387	19.38	1.396	1.355	14.45	13.98

Fig. 5, curve 15 has been shown in curve 16 on a magnified scale in the same figure. In all cases, the cataphoretic speed of the sol continually decreases with the concentrations of the electrolyte. Unlike the case of aluminium hydroxide sol, no initial increment of the cataphoretic speed of the sol at very low concentrations of potassium chloride has been observed in this case. The above data also show that a critical coagulation potential does not exist.

SUMMARY.

1. The speed-dilution curve of arsenious sulphide sol is S-shaped in form. This peculiar behaviour cannot be reconciled with the theoretical point of view which regards colloidal arsenious sulphide to behave as an electrolyte, *viz.*, as a weak acid.

2. The cataphoretic speeds of silicic acid sols vary greatly from sol to sol and is smaller than that of the usual suspensoid sols. Sometimes a certain length near about the boundary or the whole of the silicic acid sol sets to a gel in the tube. The gel formation is hastened on passage of current through the sol.

The cataphoretic speeds of silicic acid sol (A) increase on dilution of the sol.

* A sudden drop in the potential gradient on the addition of electrolytes is observed. This has been dealt with fully in a separate paper.

† Partial coagulation took place.

3. The cataphoretic speeds of aluminium hydroxide sol (A) increases on the dilution of the sol. The specific conductivity of the sol, however, decreases with dilution.

4. With sample (A) of aluminium hydroxide sol, the cataphoretic speed increases at 0.001N-KCl but decreases at higher concentrations up to 0.1N (Coagulation region). With K_2SO_4 however there is a continuous decrease. The cataphoretic speeds at the coagulation region differ considerably for the two electrolytes and show that the assumption of a critical coagulation potential is not justifiable.

5. Measurement of cataphoretic speeds of ferric hydroxide sol in contact with KCl, K_2SO_4 , NaCl continually decrease with increasing concentrations of the above electrolytes. These observations also show that a critical coagulation potential does not exist.

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